

Deliverable 4.1

Methodology of the Rethinkerspaces

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RETHINK D4.1

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Table of Contents

1.	Introduction	4
2.	Framing the Project	5
2.1	Background	5
2.2	Aim and approach of Rethink	5
3.	Rethinkerspaces.....	7
3.1	Transdisciplinary approach	8
3.2	Community of practice	9
3.3	Transformative learning	9
4.	Steps and tools.....	11
4.1.	Step 1: ESTABLISH the Rethinkerspaces as part of the institution (January-March 2019).....	12
4.2.	Step 2: RETHINKERSPACE STAKEHOLDER MAP (April- May 2019).....	12
4.3.	Step 3: BUILD the Rethinkerspace (May-June 2019)	15
4.4.	Step 4: UNDERSTAND the landscape (May 2019)	18
4.5.	Step 5: DEVELOP & EXPERIMENT with new approaches.....	21
4.6.	Step 6: SYNTHESIZE AND TRAIN for transformation.....	21
5.	Communication and engagement	23
5.1.	Internal communication:.....	23
5.2.	External communication and stakeholder engagement.....	23
5.3.	Impact figures.....	24
6.	List of activities.....	26
6.1.	Research activities carried out within the Rethinkerspaces:.....	26
6.2.	Workshops to be carried out in the Rethinkerspaces:.....	26
6.3.	Workshops carried out with the Rethinkerspaces coordinators:	27
7.	ETHICS requirements.....	28
8.	Reporting	29
	Annex 1: Sample informed Consent Form	30
	Annex 2: Reporting	31

1. Introduction

Science communication is at a decisive moment in its history. The emergence of digital communication has shaken-up the field offering new opportunities but also, increasingly, leads to new challenges. More importantly it has led to a thorough transformation of the landscape. RETHINK aims to provide a view of this new landscape and answer some of its pressing issues. Our work will be to identify barriers and inequalities that are hindering open and reflexive connections between science and society. Moreover, we will develop new strategies and tools that encourage evidence-based transformations in science communication practice as well as guide relevant policies to further open Research & Innovation (R&I) to society.

Deliverable 4.1 is the first step in this process. It will lay down the foundations for the seven national hubs of the project. These hubs, called *Rethinkerspaces*, will generate a deep and wide overview of 'their' national science communication landscape and act as testbeds and validation mechanisms for the research results of the project. Via their local communities, the Rethinkerspaces will be in charge of creating communities of inquiry to acquire insights into the emerging science communication landscape, map networks, actors, roles and repertoires, contribute to understand sensemaking practices and test a new quality of interactions framework. Besides, they will experiment with new strategies and train other actors in new ways of science communication. In order to do so, we aspire to mobilize heterogeneous groups of at least 15 participants in seven European countries (Italy (ZML), the Netherlands (VU), Poland (CSC), Portugal (ITQB NOVA), Serbia (CPN), Sweden (V&A) and the United Kingdom (UWE)). The Rethinkerspace will become a learning environment to engage in a collective process of inquiry, experimentation and reflective learning.

The work of the Rethinkerspaces is crucial for the entire project, and accordingly establishing and managing them, just as important. We have designed this deliverable to support and accompany the Rethinkerspaces throughout in this process. It presents a methodology for the work of the Rethinkerspaces, including the necessary tools for each of the phases.¹

The deliverable is structured as follows: in order to place the work of the Rethinkerspaces in context, it starts of by framing the project. Next the reader will find a description of the theoretical and conceptual underpinnings of the Rethinkerspaces and practical implications hereof. This is followed by the necessary steps to create such a hub including tools and exercises as well as the different activities and workshops that the seven Rethinkerspaces will have to carry out. Finally, the ethics dimension, communication tools and impact figures each of the Rethinkerspaces needs to reach are described.

¹ Part of the research is still being designed, some tools will come at a later stage and will be added to this document. This is particularly the case for steps 4, 5 and 6 of the Rethinkerspace methodology.

2. Framing the Project

2.1 Background

Open and productive interactions between science and society are vital for a healthy democracy. The relationship between science and the rest of society is a crucial aspect of how our society develops and addresses societal challenges such as food security and climate change. Fruitful interactions between science and society are not straightforward, as recent controversies have shown.ⁱ

We need an approach to science communication that is able to nurture interactions between science and society in an open and reflexive way. However, the science communication landscape itself is undergoing deep and fundamental changes due to two interrelated changes. First, the boundaries between science and society have become blurred. Interactions and interfaces between science and other fields in society such as economics, politics, art and culture have become more numerous and diverse. Second, digitalization has revolutionized the science communication landscape. It has fundamentally changed how scientists; other R&I stakeholders and a variety of publics interact and communicate.

These developments require us to rethink the newly emerging science communication landscape to ensure the quality of interactions between the actors involved. In the context of emerging digital media, it has become relatively easy to disregard scientific evidence as ‘just another opinion’.ⁱⁱ At the same time, at least part of the scientific community still struggles with the lingering yet false assumption that deficits in public knowledge (referred to as the ‘deficit model’) are the central factor in social conflicts and controversies about science, while in fact underlying interests, moral values and cultural beliefs have a much larger role in shaping public views about science.ⁱⁱⁱ

It is a time of great opportunity to open science and create meaningful connections with society if the right conditions are created. The RETHINK project encompasses today’s key manifestations of science communication with a particular focus on the digital sphere where scientists, science communicators and various publics exchange information, ideas and concerns and where challenges, but also opportunities exist to open up science and form meaningful connections.

2.2 Aim and approach of Rethink

How can the theory and practice of science communication contribute to a productive relationship between science and society, supporting the opening up of research and innovation practices whilst simultaneously maintaining and improving the quality of interactions amongst the actors involved? Professional science communicators have always been key catalysts of meaningful interactions at the interface between science and society, building bridges between experts, policymakers and society as a whole. How can they continue to play this vital role in the newly emerging landscape bringing together a seemingly endless variety of actors, activities, communicative spaces and sensemaking practices?

RETHINK D4.1

Against this backdrop, the RETHINK project aspires to rethink science communication, both its theory and practice, to accommodate the major challenges to the individual and collective process of making sense about science. We focus on everyday practices of making sense about science and recognize that sense-making is not only about basic scientific knowledge, but also about a range of other aspects, such as how science works, the limits of scientific knowledge, the important of economic, social, political and ethical dimensions and the legitimacy of a variety of values and perspectives that are present in the public conversation about science. Scientific understanding may provide part of the solution to a social problem, but not all of it. An open and reflexive approach to the complexities of sensemaking is crucial to address social conflicts and controversies arising in the interaction between science and society. Even if past years have seen a growing number of participation mechanisms and deliberative forums mushroom, these coexist with a big number of European citizens that rely on mediated communication to make sense about science in relation to social issues.

With these notions in mind, a guiding principle of RETHINK is that the contextual knowledge of citizens across the EU should play a vital role in shaping future scientific and technological developments and the sharing of this knowledge should be facilitated. We eventually aim to improve the quality of interactions between science and society by providing concrete recommendations and training resources for nurturing open and reflexive science-society interfaces. The following diagram explains how the project is structured and how it works towards its final goal “A European science communication ecosystem that is open, inclusive, reflexive and adaptive”.

3. Rethinkerspaces

RETHINK thus aims to improve the quality of interactions between science and society by providing recommendations and training resources for nurturing open and reflexive science-society interfaces. How can science communicators play their vital role in the newly emerging landscape?

According to the philosophy of the RETHINK project a wide arrange of actors need to work together in order to find meaningful answers to this question. Moreover, the involvement of practitioners ensures that their legitimate interests, motivations and commercial realities are considered. Accordingly, RETHINK will establish seven hubs, called Rethinkerspaces, which will generate a thorough and widespread overview of the national science communication landscape and act as testbeds and validation mechanisms. Such Rethinkerspaces will be established in universities and science engagement organizations from seven European countries that together present a wide range of the European science communication landscape: Italy (ZML), the Netherlands (VU), Poland (CSC), Serbia (CPN), Sweden (V&A), and the UK (UWE).

Each of the Rethinkerspaces will have to identify a group of at least 15 relevant individuals that can form the core of the Rethinkerspace. Via their local communities, Rethinkerspaces will be in charge of creating communities of inquiry to acquire insights into the emerging science communication landscape, map networks, actors, roles and repertoires, contribute to understand sensemaking practices and test a new quality of interactions framework.

The RETHINK research approach constitutes a transdisciplinary, participatory, and action-oriented perspective. The Rethinkerspaces take part in the research activities carried out in WP 1, 2 and 3 by collecting data, the analysis will be performed by project partners. The results will be fed back to the Rethinkerspaces for reflection and dialogue. The project is structured according to a basic model of reflective inquiry, consisting of three subsequent phases, that in itself contribute to building a community of inquiry and practice.

The Rethinkerspaces will develop their reflective practice by taking part in three phases of inquiry; understand the science communication landscape, develop and experiment with new roles and strategies, synthesize into recommendations and guidelines for scientists, practitioners and policy-makers (see diagram below).

For the *Understand phase*, the role of the Rethinkerspaces will be to bring their local perspective and input. Activities will focus on gaining insights into the new science communication landscape. This includes investigating the actors of the current and emerging landscapes, their roles, relations and repertoires. The research will also investigate the dynamics of sensemaking practice and of trust and expertise. Finally teaching and training will also be examined.

For the *Develop and Experiment phase*, the Rethinkerspaces aim at designing strategies to address the complexities identified during the previous phase. In addition, they will be also in charge of running a small set of experiments and testing new ways of doing science communication adapting them to the local perspective and proving their validity.

For the final phase, *Synthesize and Train*, Rethinkerspaces will train their local stakeholder community to implement the new methodologies and strategies developed in the previous phase in order to establish improved interactions between science and society. These methodologies and strategies have been developed and tested in a shared learning process by the Rethinkerspaces in previous phases.

The Rethinkerspaces have three common features that will be explained in the next sections, namely the Rethinkerspace as: 1) employing a transdisciplinary approach, 2) becoming a community of practice and last, 3) aspiring to transformative learning.

3.1 Transdisciplinary approach

The problems that are currently affecting science-society interactions cross the boundaries of several disciplines and communities. Rethinking science communication therefore requires a transdisciplinary approach that connects scientific and non-scientific perspectives in a joint process of inquiry and learning. Transdisciplinarity stands for ‘a form of learning and problem-solving in co-operation between different parts of society and science’. Solutions are devised in collaboration, or co-created, by multiple stakeholders of various disciplines.

A transdisciplinary approach not only transcends single or individual disciplines, but also the boundaries of the scientific community, to an approach that includes the incorporation of the views

RETHINK D4.1

of multiple scientific and nonscientific actors, professionals and amateurs. These individual actors should come from a range of perspectives and backgrounds, for example scientists, science journalists, bloggers, influencers, DIY-ers, artists, public engagement professionals, policymakers at local and national level, science funders. They all bring their own knowledge and expertise to the Rethinkerspaces, of which the other members will learn and subsequently integrate this ‘new’ knowledge into their own field of expertise.

3.2 Community of practice

The concept of the Rethinkerspaces is based on the Community of Practice (CoP) approach to social learning. When multiple stakeholders share a passion, interest or a sense of urgency to progress together – often with respect to a specific topic – and form a community around a shared domain of interest this is called a Community of Practice (CoP). Through mutual engagement and by working on challenges in their shared domain of interest, members of a CoP generate innovative and creative solutions, and new practices. The most successful CoPs (1) are driven by intrinsically motivated members, (2) stimulate the imagination of participants, that is they promote ‘out of the box’ thinking, (3) are flexible and continuously adapt their activities in relation to the context at the boundaries of the CoP, and (4) develop collaborative relationships and mutual norms between its members.

3.3 Transformative learning

The challenges identified, the rapidly changing science communication landscape, the implications of digitalization, and the crossing and blurring of boundaries between science and society, require a change of the science communication system. The current system is not arranged and equipped to address these challenges adequately, due to barriers:

- At the practical level: motivations and competencies to engage in open dialogue and transdisciplinary research are often lacking.
- At the structural level: barriers relate to the (dis)incentive structures that scientists have to obey to, such as metrics, career opportunities and so on.
- At the cultural level: conflicting ideologies of science and the role of science in society complicate change.

Indeed, research on socio-technological change has shown that system transformation will only happen if multiple initiatives challenge the “status quo” at all three levels.^{iv} In this project we approach it as a *transformative learning process*. Hence the aim for RETHINK is to co-develop a network of science communicators (and other relevant actors in the science-society landscape) that has transformative capacities in realizing a future proof science communication landscape across Europe. Practically this means that (1) the coordinators and members of the Rethinkerspaces themselves become ambassadors of transformation, and foremost (2) that the Rethinkerspaces each facilitate the emergence of a transformative network(s) as well. Through the trainings and tools provided to the Rethinkerspaces during the life cycle of RETHINK, the coordinators will become equipped to facilitate the emergence of new transformative network in their own science communication environment.

RETHINK D4.1

In order to facilitate learning, Rethinkerspaces should provide a safe space for discussion and also, be the place to find solutions for existing and upcoming challenges. The activities and events organized by the Rethinkerspaces should enable a form of learning that transforms problematic frames of reference to make them more inclusive, reflective and open to change. This requires delving underneath the 'surface' of observable actions and events and reflect on the underlying level of assumptions, values and beliefs that people adhere to. By setting up a learning environment in which these questions are raised and addressed, a new and shared vision on the science communication landscape will emerge, creating possibilities for reflection-in-action.

In this process, new knowledge is obtained – of which the Rethinkerspace members may, again, learn. In this way, knowledge creation is a continuous and shared process. Members will obtain new knowledge, test it in their own practices or field of expertise, and bring their new experiences back to the Rethinkerspace. They are the incubator of shared learning processes that can bring about new knowledge.

In practice, this learning process is centered around a series of workshops, four in total, plus a number of other activities some of which have already been defined and some of which will be defined throughout the course of the project once the research has yielded its first results (the activities that have already been identified and developed are included in section.

4. Steps and tools

We have structured RETHINK around three research work packages and a timeline divided in three phases. For clarity, the strategy for establishing and running a Rethinkerspace has been broken down into 6 steps that fit into the different phases. Each step is linked to the different work packages and research phases and built around a series of workshops and some research activities.

- a) Step 1: Establish the Rethinkerspaces as part of the institution
- b) Step 2: Rethinkerspace stakeholder map
- c) Step 3: Build the Rethinkerspace
- d) Step 4: Understand the landscape
- e) Step 5: Experiment with new approaches
- f) Step 6: Train for transformation

The following diagram explains how the different work packages, phases and steps are linked:

4.1. Step 1: ESTABLISH the Rethinkerspaces as part of the institution (January-March 2019)

Objective: Appoint a coordinator and a team to lead the project.

As part of this step, the host institution will appoint a Rethinkerspace coordinator. This person will be the central contact point of the Rethinkerspace host organisation. Once nominated and familiarised with the project, the coordinator should then present the project and its objectives to the rest of the team in the institution. Ideally, the coordinator will leverage existing staff meetings and opportunities to expose the project to key members in the institution: all of them should be a priori interested in the advancement of the science communication field and the Rethinkerspace would benefit from this positive predisposition. Establishing a team within the institution will be essential for the following steps of the project.

4.2. Step 2: RETHINKERSPACE STAKEHOLDER MAP (April- May 2019)

Objective: identify and map all the local stakeholders

Once the first step is completed and the Rethinkerspace has a coordinator and a team appointed, you will have to locate and map relevant stakeholders at the local and national level, for three purposes 1) understand the Rethinkerspace environment, 2) find and recruit Rethinkerspace members, 3) getting started on the WP1 research task of mapping the landscape.

WP1 is carrying out a scoping study of the science communication landscape in each of the seven countries covered by RETHINK (Step 4 Understand the landscape) and the stakeholder mapping performed in this step will be of help for that activity and vice versa. Whereas WP1 will focus on the digital sphere of the science communication field, the mapping in this step shouldn't be limited to that specific area. The mapping should look at the different stakeholder groups that were identified at the proposal stage and take into consideration the local specificities because even though the project focuses mainly on digital communication, stakeholders that contribute to science-society interfaces are also of our interest and this interaction is potentially affected by digital communication as well.

The groups identified are the following:

RETHINK D4.1

To do the mapping, consider the type of stakeholders that have been laid out in the figure above and make sure you identify those existing within your local context.

You should organise a meeting or a workshop with the rest of the team working on the project. The first part of the mapping will start with the identification of stakeholders.

1. Brainstorm and build a list of stakeholders:

You will have to brainstorm together to come up with a list of institutions and people. Write the names in sticky notes and place them on a big sheet of paper. Keep in mind that this list will evolve throughout the project as the different outcomes and activities start happening. At this stage you shouldn't pick but include everyone who currently has an interest in the project and do not forget those that may become interested in the future. Where possible, identify individuals. Revise past and ongoing projects and activities. Are there relevant individuals you should add to the list?

Once you have completed this map with the inner group working in RETHINK, share your results more widely (with the rest of the team) and if possible gather input from other staff members that might help you complete the list and identify individuals within the institutions you did not know who to contact.

2. Analyse the list:

You should analyze all of the stakeholders that you have identified under this lens.

Once you have your initial list, you should further analyse your findings to understand their relevance and the perspective they bring to understand science communication.

Taking into consideration the project's objectives and goals, as well as its methodology WP4 has identified the following criteria as relevant to the project. Use them to analyse your stakeholders.

- Diversity of stakeholders
 - Area of activity: what is the area of activity of your stakeholder?
 - Implicit science communication model: What model of science communication is the stakeholder using? This will help you understand their underlying assumptions as well.

In the Description of Action, we have identified 4 models of science communication.

Model	Direction	Dominant Framework	Communication
Dissemination	1-way/ linear	Science	Transfer
Dialogue	2-way/ linear	Science + public	Exchange
Participation	3-way/ multi-directional	Multiple Frameworks	Interpretation
Co-creation	x-way/ omni-directional	Emergent Frameworks	Meaning-making

For the first two items, diversity would be the element you should value most. Have as varied and representative a group of stakeholders as possible.

For the next three items (commitment, influence and pioneer), the following graphs will help position the stakeholder and analyze if the person is relevant and suitable for the Rethinkerspace. The areas shaded in red indicate the stakeholders that are not so relevant to fulfill RETHINK's objectives and in green those stakeholders that are more relevant for the project.

- Commitment

- Open to change: Are your stakeholders willing to change the way they do science communication? Are they willing to experiment with new approaches and implement them?
- Engaged in science communication: Do your stakeholders believe in the importance of science communication? Are they committed to the advancement of the science communication field?

- Influence

- Influence on science communication professionals: Is your stakeholder a relevant member of the community? Does the person have the capacity to shape the ideas and approaches of other members of the science communication community?
- Influence on the publics: Has the person got the capacity to influence the ideas and concerns of the general publics?

RETHINK D4.1

- Pioneer

- Is your stakeholder an early adopter of new ways of doing science communication?
Is the person/institution a trendsetter?
- Can this person act as a proxy of its specific stakeholder group?

3. Select all relevant actors from the list:

This activity is a necessary and crucial step to work on the next ones, so the more complete this mapping the better the foundations of the project.

4.3. Step 3: BUILD the Rethinkerspace (May-June 2019)

Objective: Select important stakeholders and attract them to your Rethinkerspace

As part of this step, the Rethinkerspace coordinator will start to actually work on recruiting the stakeholders. For that they will have to devise a recruitment process, an engagement plan and create an action plan to be successful in attracting a good group of individuals to carry out the research at the local level.

4.1.1. Recruitment process

The minimum number of stakeholders for any given Rethinkerspace is of 15 participants. Participants need to come from different backgrounds and should ideally cover the full spectrum described in the proposal (see figure with stakeholder groups in the previous step p. 13). The recruitment of the members of your Rethinkerspace should be based on the mapping of the landscape carried out in WP1. Take your stakeholder list (in sticky notes) and place them in the following stakeholder map (See annex 3):

Figure 1

Place all the stakeholders according to the importance for the work of your Rethinkerspace and how they have ranked with the criteria identified in the previous step. You should aim to have a mix of stakeholders with those criteria in mind.

4.1.2. Engagement plan: Creating an Action plan using Personas

Once your stakeholder map is completed and your ideal Rethinkerspace participants have been identified and placed in the map, the coordinator should then establish the type of relationship they have with the persons or institutions they have mapped. Trust will be the central element to understand and analyze. Our recommendation would be to start with your existing network of partners with whom you have an established relationship. But this project should also contribute to extending your network and help you build new relationships. Keep in mind the importance of building a trustworthy relationship with them, you will need to be transparent about the project and its objectives and take time as these new relationships will not thrive overnight. How are you going to approach the stakeholders? When? For that you will need to build an action plan.

4.1.3. The action plan

Once all of these relationships have been mapped, the next activity will be to create a plan of the different actions you have to undertake to involve them including: a timeline, the stakeholder group that needs to be involved and what are the objectives in terms of engagement. A key part will be to identify existing barriers you may encounter when trying to engage the selected stakeholders and then devise actions to overcome them. A good tool to determine the barriers will be to use personas to characterize the different stakeholders. For this exercise, a persona will describe a

RETHINK D4.1

stakeholder group in a way that is easy to understand and empathize with. Describe both the person as a human being (background story, personality, interests, etc.) and as a stakeholder in context of the science communication ecosystem (needs, expectations, etc.)

Personas: This template gives an example of what a persona could look like (See annex 3)

STAKEHOLDER PROFILE

The form is titled "STAKEHOLDER PROFILE" and consists of nine dashed-line boxes arranged in two rows. The top row contains four boxes: 1. A box for a profile picture with a circular icon and a "Name:" label. 2. A box labeled "Who am I?" with a person icon. 3. A box labeled "3 reasons for me to engage with the co-creation Lab" with a signpost icon showing one arrow with a checkmark and one with an 'X'. 4. A box labeled "3 reasons for me NOT to engage with the co-creation Lab" with a signpost icon showing one arrow with a checkmark and one with an 'X'. The bottom row contains five boxes: 1. "My interests" with a heart and thumbs-up icon. 2. "My personality" with a hand holding a smile icon. 3. "My skills" with a laurel wreath icon. 4. "My dreams" with a steering wheel icon. 5. "My social environment" with a group of people icon. At the bottom left is the European Union flag and text: "This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824573". At the bottom right is a Creative Commons license icon.

Action plan: Once the stakeholder profile is completed, the coordinator and its team will have to create an engagement plan. The following template can serve as a guide (See annex 3). Keep in mind that emails will probably not suffice especially with stakeholders you already don't know. Use a mix of digital and face-to-face contacts.

RETHINK D4.1

landscape of digital science communication across Europe, looking at which individuals and institutions are doing the communication and the form this takes. These individuals might be journalists, scientists or bloggers who write in their bedroom. Anyone. The institutions might be science centres, museums, or research centres. Again, anyone. This mapping will be conducted using a rigorous online search process in seven countries – Italy, the Netherlands, UK, Sweden, Poland, Serbia and Portugal. UWE which leads WP1 will prepare a report on the findings and the Rethinkerspaces are expected to look at a draft of this to check that nothing is missing, especially any innovative science communicators and techniques.

Besides, WP1 is also developing a questionnaire that will look to find out the practices, motivations, incentives and disincentives that those engaged in digital science communication have. This questionnaire will also ask about how science communicators develop connections with their audiences; particularly audiences that don't typically engage with science material. It will be distributed to some of the science communicators identified in the mapping, but will also ask members of the Rethinkerspaces to help distribute the questionnaire among their network (colleagues and associates in their country). Some of the communicators identified will also be invited to take part in interviews to dig a little deeper into what they do. At the end of this, WP1 will produce a written report on their findings. Finally, they will conduct one or two small experiments in their own practice to test new behaviours.

The collection of data will follow a protocol devised by UWE in WP1 and that will be shared with the Rethinkerspaces to be implemented by a nominated person. This person does not need to be the coordinator but will most likely work at the Rethinkerspace institution. The second part is related to sensemaking practices. In WP2 we aim to investigate the sensemaking practices of societies on science. Next, we will explore barriers and opportunities to open-up those sensemaking practices. A part of this is examining ways for scientists and R&I stakeholders to engage in science communication. Lastly, all findings will contribute to the development of strategies for good practices in opening-up science to society, or in other words, to enhance the quality of interactions between science, politics, media and society.

WP2 will ask Rethinkerspaces to contribute to the local work for this task. In the first place they will have to identify relevant experts and to coordinate interviews with them. These interviews will be carried out by WP2 representatives and will need to be performed in English. Finally, for this part of the task, Rethinkerspaces will also be asked to help the WP2 team in analysing the conversation.

The third line of investigation deals with issues such as the uncertainty of information and its related quality changes of science communication. The aim is to develop training programs which refer to these challenges.

RETHINK D4.1

First, WP3 will examine the landscape of teaching and training in Europe. Following that, they will run a comparison of programs that address different target groups (scientists, professional communicators) and to which extent these include alternative communicators like bloggers. The leading question for this part of the research is if different programs already teach how to communicate science to diverse parts of the public and at times of uncertainty of information. This will be done on the basis of analyzing existing documents of the program and will be complemented by a survey directed to the training program lead.

Sensemaking

Sensemaking is the fundamental way by which we develop an understanding of a complex reality. Due to digitalization and blurring boundaries in the science communication ecosystem, scientific facts are more often under public scrutiny. Scientific evidence is more often disregarded as ‘just another opinion’. Online, everybody can be a journalist. An overload of information leaves audiences with questions. Although scientific evidence is present, science will not always give answers to important questions like: ‘Who can I trust? What information is accurate? And what should we do with this information?’. This indicates that next to scientific facts other considerations are at the basis of finding suitable solutions for complex societal problems. For example, understanding the prerequisites and dimensions of trust and accuracy in facilitating a constructive societal conversation. Complex interactions between science, politics, media and the wider public – or in other words the larger context of societal problems – are of importance here. In RETHINK’s objective to improve the quality of the interactions between science, politics, media and the public, it is key to understand how people make sense of science. For example: when a young mother reads articles on brain growth in order to understand what is happening to her prematurely born baby, this information is not interpreted from a scientific perspective, but according to her previous knowledge and understanding of her child. This illustrates that engagement with science is context specific and that the understanding, or sense-making, of science differs in various contexts. Sensemaking is an important dimension of how society shapes its view on science and as such also the way in which we address societal issues.

At the same time, experts will be interviewed to understand the needs from science communication training dealing with this changing science communication landscape. Based on this research (and on the results of WP1 and 2) WP3 will develop a framework for the assessment of quality in science communication training programs. Criteria will be developed in such a way that they adjust to the specific needs and features of the new landscape (i.e. increased heterogeneity, fragmentation, complexity, uncertainty).

The next step will be to decide which training modules could be useful for teaching the “RETHINK perspective“. Once selected, the project will develop and test training resources. The trainings will be integrated into existing undergraduate and postgraduate programs at VUA, UWE and SML, and will be tested offline and online within the Rethinkerspaces.

Rethinkerspaces will contribute to the mapping of existing training programmes in their countries, and to the testing of trainings.

RETHINK D4.1

This step is linked with research carried out in WP1, WP2, and WP3 and with workshop #1 and workshop #2 (listed in [section 6](#))

4.5. Step 5: DEVELOP & EXPERIMENT with new approaches

The research activities aim at developing new strategies to improve the quality of science communication and for that we will develop new ways of doing science communication. As part of the strategies' refinement process the project has arranged a set of small-sized experiments. These experiments will be key in testing new strategies that have been developed to respond to the needs identified in the research: a new role typology, new trainings as well as new interaction techniques including conversation and reflection tools among others.

The Rethinkerspaces have been tasked with testing the new approaches developed within the research work packages. The three main lines of research will benefit from experimental exercises in the Rethinkerspaces:

- Role definitions describe the contributions that actors can make to improve the interactions between science and society. For instance, in the past, science journalist would act as gatekeepers and translators of scientific content. In this new landscape, what could be their new role?
- Strategies to open-up are important because discussions about science are about visions and values and not about facts. And this is being discussed implicitly, through the discussion of the facts. The underlying assumption is that conversations would be more meaningful and productive if we were to discuss the values as well. Research will show us how people make sense of science in their everyday environment, knowing the facts we will develop strategies to make the discussions more open.
- Quality of interactions framework: The quality of interactions between science and society can no longer be safeguarded or even measured by traditional means; therefore, a new quality of interactions framework will be needed.

Each of the Rethinkerspaces in collaboration with the stakeholders will have to run at least experiment (a small sized exercise for individuals or small groups in which they try out new behavior as part of their science communication practice) that will be designed by the research work packages in each of the areas described above.

However, the exact shape of the experiments will be defined later in the project once the first research exercises have finished.

This step is linked with research carried out in WP1, WP2 and WP3 and with workshop #3 (listed in [section 6](#))

4.6. Step 6: SYNTHESIZE AND TRAIN for transformation

This step is divided into two different activities, on the one hand the Danish Board of Technology together with the research work packages leads will synthesize the project's outcomes and transform them into guidelines for different stakeholders. Rethinkerspaces are expected to share these guidelines at the local level.

RETHINK D4.1

On the other hand, once the research is completed, Rethinkerspaces will be expected to first attend a train-the-trainers workshop at the Ecsite conference in 2021. This workshop will equip them to gain practical knowledge about how to conduct trainings to improve science communication activities of other practitioners. Then, they will have to deliver a training workshop to their Rethinkerspace participants and other relevant stakeholders to share the knowledge gained during the project.

This step is linked to workshop #4 (listed in [section 6](#))

5. Communication and engagement

Communication, both internal and external, stakeholder engagement and impact are going to be key success factors of the project. In this section we present and define these concepts as well as quantify the impact each of the Rethinkerspaces will have to achieve in the framework of the project

5.1. Internal communication:

In order to ensure a smooth implementation of the project and a good liaison between research work packages and Rethinkerspaces, Ecsite will put in place a series of tools to guarantee the necessary alignment between the different strands of work that will be key in obtaining good results. Ecsite and VU will submit regular updates and organise calls to keep them up to date with the advancement of the project.

5.2. External communication and stakeholder engagement

RETHINK has its own general dissemination activities led by WP6. Besides the work carried out by the project as part of that work package, each of the Rethinkerspaces will have to contribute to the overall dissemination and communication in their own local context. But above all, they will also have to involve and engage a number of stakeholders over time. The number and type of stakeholders that need to be engaged has been defined [in section 6](#) of this document. It is important to distinguish between engagement, dissemination and communication.

- **Engagement:** the direct involvement of scientists, other R&I stakeholders, practitioners such as science journalists and public engagement professionals, bloggers, artists and DIY scientists.
- **Dissemination:** public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium, including publications and external presentations.
- **Communication:** taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting RETHINK itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

	Engagement	Dissemination	Communication
Definition	Engagement is about involving societal actors (including citizens) in the decision-making process or in the research process itself . Public engagement is about bringing on board the widest possible diversity of actors.	Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.	Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results . It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences , including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.
Objective	To elicit input in the form of opinions, judgments, decisions and actions that informs processes, outcomes and policies.	Transfer knowledge and results with a view to enable others to use and take up results , thus maximizing the impact.	Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits.
Focus	Assure that representatives from affected Stakeholder groups (including users and citizens) are part of the decision making process .	Describe and ensure results available for others to use.	Inform about and promote the project and its results / successes.
Audience	Stakeholders that are affected and can benefit from results and processes.	Audiences that may take an interest in the potential use of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partner, policy makers).	Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community incl. media and the broad public.

Defining engagement, dissemination and communication²

5.3. Impact figures

Taking into consideration the previous definition of engagement, communication and dissemination, each of the Rethinkerspaces should aim to reach at least the following number of people:

² Adapted from: [Making the most of your H2020 Project](#) and [Science, Society and Engagement – An e-Anthology](#)

RETHINK D4.1

STAKEHOLDERS	Engagement				Dissemination and communication	Total
	Members of the RS	Experiments in the RS	Training participants	Reached by Synthesis		
R & I actors , including engaged or non-engaged individuals, PR offices, research institutions & businesses	4	18	86	8	167	283
Practitioners , including journalists, media organisations, educators, science centers	6	26	172	65	445	714
Citizens , including citizen scientists, DIY scientists, interest groups, hard to reach citizens	4	43	58	15	123	243
Enablers , including policy makers, at institutional, national and EU level, funders, publishers	3	12	12	36	43	106
Total	17	99	328	124	778	1346

6. List of activities

Each Rethinkerspace needs to carry out at least the following research and engagement activities. For the purpose of this deliverable we have divided it into workshops and other activities connected to each of the work packages.

6.1. Research activities carried out within the Rethinkerspaces:

WP1:

- implementation of a protocol to map science communication actors, forms, platforms, tools, content type and audiences.
- An online questionnaire to be shared with your network

WP2:

- Contribute to the collection of good practices on the opening up of science
- Identification of 4 main actors to be interviewed
- Support VU in liaising with these actors to organise interviews

WP3:

- Identify the most relevant science communication trainings, gather information about them and identify a contact person.

6.2. Workshops to be carried out in the Rethinkerspaces:

The formats of the workshops as well as the exercises to be carried out will be designed and compiled by Ecsite and the research partners.

- Workshop #1: This workshop will serve as the kick-off meeting of the Rethinkerspace. During this workshop stakeholders will also give input on the results of the report on the working practices, motivations and challenges of those engaged in science communication (September 2019)
 - Exercise 1
 - Exercise 2
- Workshop #2: This workshop will be mainly focused on contributing to the development of the role typology of the new science communication, collecting best sensemaking practices. (May 2020)
 - Exercise 1
 - Exercise 2
- Workshop #3: This activity will focus on the experimentation. In this workshop, Rethinkerspaces' coordinators will present to their stakeholders' possible experimental strategies of opening up. (March 2021)
 - Exercise 1

RETHINK D4.1

- Exercise 2
- Workshop #4: During this final workshop, the coordinators will present the results of the project and train the Rethinkerspace participants in new ways of doing science communication (MX 20XX)
 - Exercise 1
 - Exercise 2

6.3. Workshops carried out with the Rethinkerspaces coordinators:

- Extra training workshop to share methodologies to carry out Workshop 2 and 3.
- Train the trainers: this workshop will be carried out at the Ecsite conference of 2021. During this preconference, coordinators will be trained in new and better ways of carrying out science communication activities. With this training they will be able to deliver trainings to their stakeholders and multiply the results of the project.

7. ETHICS requirements

The Rethinkerspaces will carry out small-sized experiments, contextualising the developed models, frameworks, strategies and resources (WP1, 2, 3). These experiments will reach out to scientists, practitioners, citizens and enablers. The experiments will be reflected upon in learning workshops with the entire range of stakeholder groups being represented.

To perform this, all Rethinkerspaces will have to follow the procedure described in Deliverable 8.2, Ethics Requirement. As stated there, all of the Rethinkerspaces *“must obtain informed consent from the subjects of their study prior to performing the research itself, being it an interview, questionnaire, focus group, dialogue or other project activity, for data sharing and for long- term preservation. The informed consent form includes a section on the collection and storage of personal data in databases, a statement regarding the period of storage of data and possible use for future research. Furthermore, participants will be informed that they, or their legal representative, may request data to be deleted when this data has not already been used in publications or presentations. Hard copy informed consent forms should be scanned and encrypted before storing the forms on the institutions internal system. Hard copy forms should be stored in a locked file cabinet.”*

An example of an Informed Consent form is included in Annex 1 of this deliverable. The consent form is just an example and will have to be adapted to the local regulations of each of the Rethinkerspace institutions.

8. Reporting

After each of the workshops the coordinators will have to fill in a report including a description of the event, description of the stakeholders that attended (Annex 2). For each of the workshops of the project we will also ask the coordinators with a more detailed report concerning the research activities to be carried out.

Event report	Deadline: 14 days after the event
Early warning	7 days before the event
Reminder 1	7 days after the end of the event
Reminder 2	10 days after the end of the event

Annex 1: Sample informed Consent Form

RETHINK

De Boelelaan 1105

1081 HV AMSTERDAM

Permission to Use Audio and/or Video Recordings

Name: _____

Location: RETHINK workshop in XXX

During this workshop, you may be recorded on audio and/or videotape so that your information may be used for research within the project. You have three choices regarding the audiotape, videotape, and/or transcript of the interview. The materials may be designated either “public,” “for research only,” or “private.”

If you designate the materials “public,” your audiotape(s) or videotape(s), RETHINK may use the materials from the training for future research and your materials will remain part of its permanent collection.

If you designate the materials “for research only,” your audiotape(s) or videotape(s) will be analysed by researchers and your information will be used in studies. Your information will be reported in a way that does not identify you and your materials will be destroyed after the study is complete.

If you designate the materials “private,” the audiotape(s) or videotape(s) will never be released by RETHINK. The only records of the interview will belong solely to you.

If in the future you wish to change the status of your audiotape(s), videotape(s), and/or transcript(s), you may contact the RETHINK:

___ I hereby designate the materials as public and give permission for my audiotape(s) or videotape(s) to be used by RETHINK.

___ I hereby designate the audiotape(s) or videotape(s) for research only and give my permission for researchers to use my materials as part of the research study. I want my materials to be reported so that they will not identify me and destroyed when the study is complete.

___ I hereby designate these materials as private and do NOT give my permission for my audiotape(s) or videotape(s) to be used by RETHINK. The materials will be given to you for your own private use.

Printed name _____

Organization Name (if applicable) _____

Date _____

Signature _____

Annex 2: Reporting

Rethinkerspace – Report

Practical details

Rethinkerspace	
Event title	
Duration	
Location	
Number of participants	

Participant profiles

Professional background (journalist, mediator, scientist, other)	Stakeholder category Choose from: NGO/Citizen Organisation/Business/ Policy-maker/ Knowledge/Research institute/ Funding agency/Other (please explain)	Field of work	Gender

*Tip: You can refer to participants throughout subsequent reports on vision using this ID.

Event components & further reporting

To help us understand your workshop better, describe the activities carried out:

Event description

Context of the event (if special)	<i>e.g. if co-hosted, if held as part of a larger event etc.</i>
Description of how the workshop was run	
General outcomes	
Follow-up plans	
Lessons to share with other Rethinkerspace?	

Please paste below the agenda of your workshop and evidence of

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- ⁱ Hendriks, F., Kienhues, D., & Bromme, R. (2016). Trust in science and the science of trust. In *Trust and Communication in a Digitized World* (pp. 143-159). Springer, Cham.
- ⁱⁱ Bubela, T., Nisbet, M.C., Borchelt, et al. (2009). Science communication reconsidered. *Nature biotechnology*, 27(6), 514.
- ⁱⁱⁱ Nisbet, M.C., & Scheufele, D.A. (2009). What's next for science communication? Promising directions and lingering distractions. *American journal of botany*, 96(10), 1767-1778.
- ^{iv} Rotmans, J. et al. (2001). More evolution than revolution: transition management in public policy. *Foresight*, 3(1), 15-31.

